

Interview with Brigitta Busch, University of Vienna, 13.12.2024

CB: Cecilia Bartoli, BB: Brigitta Busch, EM: Egle Mocciaro, KL: Kristýna Lorenzová

I encountered the work of Prof. Brigitta Busch (University of Vienna) during my doctoral studies in Migration, Differences and Social Justice at the University of Palermo. My research focuses on “Plurilingualism, Multimodality and Narrative in Learning Contexts with People from Migrant Backgrounds”, and Busch's work proved to be a valuable theoretical/methodological guide for listening to and collecting linguistic biographies in this field. For this reason, when my supervisor during my period of research abroad, Prof. Egle Mocciaro (Masaryk University, Brno), suggested I visit Brigitta Busch for an interview, it seemed like a valuable opportunity. With her help and the support of doctoral colleague Kristýna Lorenzová, I prepared the questions for this interview, which took place at the University of Vienna on 13 December 2024.

We would like to thank Prof. Busch for her availability, kindness and for once again conveying the quality and passion of her work to us.

CB: In your 2012 article *The Linguistic Repertoire Revisited*, you outlined a definition of linguistic repertoire¹. Is this still valid for you now? Or has something changed?

BB: Well, there are some changes, if you like. Because there I talked about Linguistic Repertoire, and even though in the publication I was already talking about Heteroglossic Repertoire, borrowing the term from Bachtin², heteroglossic, in my sense, does not only mean different languages or different codes or registers, but heteroglossic also means different discourses and different individual voices. So, it is a much broader term. When talking about language, we need to include discourses and voices in the definition. I suppose that today I would tend to emphasise that the repertoire is heteroglossic. When we talk about a heteroglossic repertoire, we are actually also talking about other semiotic dimensions than the verbal. I think I would emphasise this much more than I did 20 years ago. And in the meantime, I have published also more about the semiotic dimension. I don't know if you've come across the work of Annelies Kusters. She is very committed in deaf studies, and she has

¹ «The repertoire can thus be seen as a hypothetical structure, which evolves by experiencing language in interaction on a cognitive and on an emotional level and is inscribed into corporal memory and embodied as linguistic habitus and which includes traces of hegemonic discourses. These discourses are expressed in categorizations that are backed up by inclusive and exclusive language ideologies. Drawing on a broad range of earlier voices, discourses, and codes, the linguistic repertoire forms a heteroglossic and contingent space of potentialities which includes imagination and desire, and to which speakers revert in specific situations» *The Linguistic Repertoire Revisited*-Applied Linguistics 2012: 1–22 Pag 19

² For Bachtin, heteroglossia refers to the plurality of voices, languages and points of view that coexist within a text, particularly in novels. For Bachtin, every word is socially situated: it carries traces of the voice of the person who uses it, but also those of other speakers, institutions and contexts. Compared to other genres, the novel is dialogical by nature: it does not present a single, monological language, but a heteroglossic repertoire, that is, a set of social languages, styles, registers, dialects and ideological discourses that enter into relationship, conflict or mutual parody.

written together with colleagues about the semiotic repertoire³. So, I think the concept is broadening.

Furthermore, in the quote you refer to, there is talk of potential, and I believe that in recent years I have been more interested in constraints, because potential comes with constraints. In past years, I have done a lot of research on traumatic experiences. I have come across much more constraints on repertoire imposed, let's say, by prohibitions or negative discursive evaluation, and I suppose I would like to emphasise them more. Although I also talk about constraints in this 2012 article, I don't think I would dare to talk only about potential in a definition anymore. Yes, I think mainly because, if you look, for example, at schools today, children are often considered deficient speakers, or deficient students, as those who do not have the right language and never will. And these are really huge constraints. So, I suppose I would insist more on this point.

CB: What you say makes me reflect on the weight of “diagnoses” made about language, which is never correct; on learning styles, which are never correct; diagnoses work as you say, as negative discourse about the person, discourse that produces a sense of exclusion and trauma.

EM: Should the entire diagnostic system at school be restructured? What do you think?

BB: Yes, exactly, because the proclaimed aim is unreachable. Like German here, which is unreachable. It is presented as unreachable. It is presented as absolutely necessary and as something to be desired, but at the same time it is presented as unreachable. I had the opportunity to investigate interviews conducted by a colleague from the education department who works in a quantitative way. She said to me: “Well, take a look at the data and see what you can get out of it as a qualitative researcher”. It was very interesting. It was about children aged 6 to 10, and from the interviews you could see very clearly that those children who were asked to speak German and who were not allowed to speak any languages other than German at school only talked about anxiety and how they were afraid of going to school and taking exams, etc. On the other hand, children in schools where there was a minimum of respect for linguistic diversity did not talk about anxiety, they felt welcome, and not *interpellated* as deficient subjects, if we want to use the Althusserian concept⁴ [from an ideology that precedes them].

³ Kusters defines the semiotic repertoire as the totality of semiotic resources that people use when communicating (such as speech, images, text, gestures, signs, gaze, facial expressions, posture, objects, and so on). This is a notion that goes beyond the traditional distinctions between “language” and “modality”: in her view, it is not just a question of linguistic varieties (spoken or signed) but of a dynamic plurality of resources that are mobilised, combined and evaluated in social contexts. Kusters, A. (2021). Introduction: the semiotic repertoire: assemblages and evaluation of resources. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 18(2), 183–189.

⁴ According to Althusser, ideology *interpellates* individuals as subjects. “Being interpellated” means being called upon to recognise oneself in a certain role or identity, within a social or institutional discourse. The individual becomes a subject when s/he responds to this call, that is, when s/he recognises herself/himself in the message addressed to her/him. In this act of recognition, the subject constitutes itself as such within ideology: it is not a pre-existing subject, but the product of the ideological call. Althusser, L. (1970). *Idéologie et appareils idéologiques d’État* (Notes pour une recherche). In *Positions* (pp. 67-125). Paris: Éditions Sociales

And because they are not interpellated as the deficient ones and those who will never achieve their goals, they also have a completely different attitude at school, towards German and language learning. And it's really striking.

CB: In your 2012 article, I read something about the desire and need for positive identification, right? Desire, as positive identification through language.

BB: Right. What I mean is that through another language, you can imagine yourself as another person. You can imagine yourself as a speaker of, let's say, French, and as someone familiar with French culture, managing in a sense to escape from the confinement in which you are temporarily caught. Language can be a fantastic vehicle to get you out of a situation that makes you feel, well, imprisonment is perhaps a strong word, but in which you feel, in a certain sense, "reduced". You probably know Claire Kramersch's work on language learning⁵.

CB: Yes, of course, the multilingual self.

BB: Yes, exactly. Claire, in her previous works, also talks a lot about desire in language learning. Claire actually took the concept from Julia Kristeva, because Julia Kristeva also speaks about desire in language learning, using the true psychoanalytical concept of desire, of *Begehren*⁶. I don't know, *Begehren*, desire, yes *Begehren*, precisely from a psychoanalytical point of view, not from the point of view of everyday language. There are many literary works, such as memoirs⁷, in which people talk about imagining themselves through language as another person and where they have found a way to develop a different perspective on their lives. As Claire says, and as Kristeva also says, perhaps Kristeva less so for language learning, but Claire certainly for language learning, this is a very strong motor for driving language learning.

And in the 2012 paper you mentioned, there is this guy, Pascal, who talks about a language prior to his first language, which was the local dialect, which for him is a language, he says, in which he could say anything he wished to say. And this is a figure that is quite often found in biographical interviews about languages and also when people explain their

⁵ For Kramersch, learning and using multiple languages does not simply produce a speaker who is "competent" in multiple codes, but a plural self, traversed by multiple cultural and emotional experiences. The multilingual subject does not "possess" languages but is inhabited by them: each language introduces a different enunciative position, a different worldview and a different way of feeling. Kramersch, C. (2009). *The Multilingual Subject: What Foreign Language Learners Say about Their Experience and Why It Matters*. Oxford University Press. Kramersch, C. (2011). The symbolic dimensions of the intercultural. *Language Teaching*, 44(3), 354–367.

⁶ *Begehren* (a German term used by Freud and taken up by Lacan) does not refer to a need or an emotion, but rather to a structural lack, which is the foundation of subjectivity itself. The subject of language is driven by a desire that can never be fully satisfied, because words always refer to an absence. Kristeva links this dynamic to the desire to learn another language, which means confronting a new symbolic order, a new way of articulating desire; the foreign language becomes a space of transference, in which the subject can reformulate their desire, shift it, translate it, re-symbolise it; the linguistic experience is therefore an analytical and transformative experience, not just a cognitive one. Kristeva, J. (1988). *Étrangers à nous-mêmes*. Paris: Fayard. Kristeva, J. (1998). *Le langage, cet inconnu: Une initiation à la linguistique*. Paris: Seuil.

language portraits⁸. They talk about an all-encompassing language, or even children have these fantasies about a language that comes naturally, etc. But unfortunately, this is an article that I only have in German. I took something from Derrida⁹, the *avant-première* langue, the language that came before the first language, if you like. Because it is a desire, it is not something that really exists, but it is the desire for communication that works in perfect harmony and unity, with universal understanding. I think it is also quite important for children to have this possibility of dreaming of these universal languages. We can also see in children's language portraits that they very often speak about languages they invent, like, I don't know, like *the language xxx* or whatever. And it is very important to let children live in this imaginary language space, because it helps them to appropriate other languages. As adults, we keep a bit of this childish pleasure, don't we? Playing around with languages and finding such spaces. I think if we allowed more playfulness, there would be less discrimination against accents and...

EM: Oh, definitely. Yes.

BB: Nowadays, teaching is always serious, governed by rules. And very often, language is fundamentally based on imposed rules. And I suppose, yes, a little more playfulness would be helpful.

EM: We held a workshop this summer. Do you remember me telling you that we organised a summer school?

BB: Yes, yes, yes.

EM: And Cecilia, together with Kristýna and another colleague from Potsdam, Marta Lupica Spagnolo, carried out a workshop using creative tools. There were many international students, and what emerged was very rich.

CB: Yes. We used language portrait, but with body mapping¹⁰.

BB: Yes, yes.

CB: It was very interesting. One girl represented Italian, which she did not know, as her mother tongue. She placed it in her chest and represented it in red in a large space. Then she thanked us because, she said, "For the first time, I can say that Italian is part of my repertoire, even though I don't speak it".

⁸ A language portrait is a visual and reflective representation of one's linguistic repertoire. .

⁹ Derrida, J. (1996). *Le monolinguisme de l'autre*. Paris: Éditions Gallilée.

¹⁰ Lupica Spagnolo, Bartoli, Lorenzová (2026). *Full-Body Language Portraits: A Creativity-Based Method to Explore Embodied Multilingualism* (currently being published)

KL: Yes, it was an opportunity to remember her, a deep connection with her grandparents' mother tongue, but one that had been “buried” in her family.

BB: There are always these really beautiful moments. Yes.

CB: Yes, so special. And at that moment I thought about your reflections on repertoire, because in this narrative I saw internalised discourses on language and family injunctions. Her grandfather was Italian, but he didn't want to speak Italian, nor did he want his children (and grandchildren) to learn it; he believed it was right for the family to integrate into American society. When she moved to Norway, she identified more (was labelled) with the language of “immigrants”, i.e. those who speak English with a different accent. She socialised more easily with other immigrants and her love for Italian and Italian culture returned, like a kind of nostalgia, or perhaps she also wanted a distant mother tongue.

KL: Yes, even her father in Norway didn't want her to speak Italian.

BB: Yes

CB: In a recent presentation¹¹, you represented the construction of repertoire and the possibility of using it as a triangular figure in which you have: at one vertex, the incorporation of social discourses and linguistic hierarchies; at another vertex, the embodied experiences and memories of past linguistic uses; and at the third vertex, the resources that are activated in interaction in the here and now. The possibility of using one's own communicative resources in a given situation is the result of the interaction of these three factors. This triangular scheme is very important to me, to my way of looking at things. In this regard, you often refer to Derrida, Bourdieu, Foucault and Butler.

BB: Yes

CB: Especially regarding the social discourse on languages and how it is incorporated by people, would you like to elaborate on this aspect?

BB: Well, I think that, you know, when we first became interested in the repertoire, we basically adopted a phenomenological approach. So, we started with Husserl and Merleau-Ponty and with this first-person perspective. But, in reality, the first-person perspective does not answer the question of how one becomes a subject. In phenomenology, the subject is already there. So, we thought we needed something to help us understand how one becomes a subject, if you wish.

Also, maybe I should say, in our empirical work, we came across a lot of misrecognitions. As I said, at school children were addressed as non-speakers, as if they had no language, as if they had the wrong language. The impact of language ideologies and, if you wish, discourses,

¹¹ Busch, B. (2020). Discourse, emotions, and embodiment. In A. De Fina & A. Georgakopoulou (Eds.), *Handbook of Discourse Studies* (pp. 327-349). Cambridge University Press

was obvious, because language ideologies are actually discourses on language and the use of language. So, we thought we had to combine the phenomenological perspective, the first-person perspective and discourse. At the time I was working on it, post-structuralism was actually on the agenda. I mean, nowadays it's nothing new, we all know the work of Foucault and so on, and Bourdieu and Derrida. But at the end of the 1990s in linguistics, this post-structuralism didn't really exist, and we started to fight for it in linguistics. We published a first special issue on post-structuralism in applied linguistics¹², and I suppose it's partly due to our personal academic socialisation that we were so interested in post-structuralism, but also because it offers the possibility of bringing together discourse and phenomenological perspectives. Today, there is an approach called subjectivation analysis¹³, which basically developed within German sociology, and which very explicitly addresses the question of how to combine together discourse and phenomenological or biographical perspectives.

CB: Yes, and you gain support for a new perspective in education/training. Recently, the phenomenological approach in education has also developed in the perspective of embodied cognition. There is a lot of research on this topic, on mirror neurons and intersubjectivity. Working on the embodied mind is a development of the phenomenological approach.

BB: The embodied perspective is really important to us.

CB: In general, neurophysiological research starts from there and leads to education. But as a study of the driving force of the mind.

BB: Well, I think we need to consider body image. In psychology, there is a concept of body image as the idea that we have of ourselves, of our body as being in the world. And I think language is a very important part of that body image. Because language on the one hand, I mean, is realised through the body. So, for instance, the voice. Without the body there is no language, because either it passes through the mouth and the voice, or it is written down and passes through the hand, or it passes through gestures and mimics in sign languages. So actually, I think that in linguistics we have completely neglected this aspect, and I think that in the perceived body image there is also the concrete possibility of designing and imagining one's own body image, one's own language in interaction. I mean, research has not yet gone that far. I published an article that you may already be familiar with: body image¹⁴.

CB: Yes, yes, I read it.

¹² *Applied Linguistics* (2012). Poststructuralism and its challenges for applied linguistics (Vol. 33, No. 5). Oxford University Press

¹³ Cf. Bosančić, S., Brodersen, F., Pfahl, L., Schürmann, L., Spies, T., & Traue, B. (Eds.). (2022). Positioning the Subject. Methodologien der Subjektivierungs- forschung / Methodologies of Subjectivation Research. Wiesbaden: Springer. Bosančić, S., Brodersen, F., Pfahl, L., Schürmann, L., Spies, T., & Traue, B. (Eds.). (2022). Positioning the Subject. Methodologien der Subjektivierungs- forschung / Methodologies of Subjectivation Research. Wiesbaden: Springer.

¹⁴ Busch, B. (2021). *The body image: taking an evaluative stance towards semiotic resources*. *International Journal of Multilingualism*.

BB: But it has not been taken up that much yet, but interest could grow, because more and more people are interested in the body or body image, and more people are interested in racialised language, racialisation via language. And recently, in the field of raciolinguistics¹⁵, a few publications draw attention to the fact that people are misrecognised in the way they speak. That they are categorised based on their appearance. There is this famous book by Rosa, Jonathan Rosa, “Looking Like a Language, Sounding Like a Race”¹⁶. I think it’s a wonderful title.

CB: It’s very interesting, yes.

BB: And I think that through raciolinguistics, we have much more to say about the body than before. About how a certain body is expected to speak or write. When you are recognised as “somebody”, there are expectations that influence.

CB: In your 2020 article¹⁷, you talk a lot about emotional dimensions. If I understand correctly, you say that what is happening here now is the connection that recalls what is inscribed, let's say, in our body image, in our deep and embodied emotional life. The concept is that emotions respond to the present and the past at the same time. It is very interesting because when a child has a block, we need to observe what is happening in the present, in the situated interaction, but also what belongs specifically to that child, to their history, which “lives” within them.

BB: Yes, yes.

CB: In interaction, in positive interaction, it is possible...

BB: Yes, soften it. Yes, yes, yes, and that’s why I’m so interested in traumatic experiences. Because very often the traumatic experience is not visible, but it is present in the body. And this does not only concern the generation that experienced the trauma, but the trauma can be transmitted. I lived for a long time in the bilingual area of Carinthia, in southern Austria. And during fascism, the Slovenian language was banned. The Slovenian population was deported to concentration camps, and many did not return. When I arrived there from Vienna and started learning Slovenian, I could not understand the attitudes towards Slovene. Because, for instance, when you enter the room, people who spoke Slovenian, for example, when a foreigner entered, they changed language to German. Many also gave up Slovenian, because many parents did not want to pass on all the troubles they have had. At first, I did not really understand why this was happening, but over time I

¹⁵ The term raciolinguistics refers to an interdisciplinary field of study that analyses the intersection between race and language, i.e. the way in which linguistic ideologies and racial ideologies co-construct and reinforce each other.

¹⁶ Rosa, J. (2019). *Looking like a language, sounding like a race: Raciolinguistic ideologies and the learning of Latinidad*. Oxford University Press.

¹⁷ Busch, B. (2020). Discourse, emotions, and embodiment. In A. De Fina & A. Georgakopoulou (Eds.), *Handbook of Discourse Studies* (pp. 327-349). Cambridge University Press

realized that the trauma had been passed on. For instance, we once had a meeting with parents, and the question was: “Do we want the end-of-year report to be issued only in German or in a bilingual version?” And I said, “Yes, why not bilingual?” And one of the mothers started to cry and said, “I don't want it to be bilingual”. And then I understood... because she also said, “I don't want it bilingual because my parents were deported as they figured on the list of Slovene-speaking people”. And suddenly it became very clear to me that people had actually abandoned the language – obviously also because of pressure, etc., etc. – but also because of that traumatic experience they somehow had to cope with. And I think this is highly emotional. It is so emotional that people cannot really talk about it. She could not really talk about it. She just cried and said she was afraid and didn't want to have her daughter on the list.

I think many children we have at school nowadays have lived through something that might have been quite traumatic for them, as they have lived through an experience that their repertoire does not fit. And this is a major crisis. Because if you suddenly find yourself in an environment where your repertoire does not fit, then you don't know how to move, and you risk being treated as somebody without a language. And being treated as someone without a language means being denied a human quality, and that can be a highly traumatic experience. I mean, it is not per se. It depends how it is lived. But it can absolutely have these consequences.

CB: This discourse is even more important in the world of refugee hosting.

BB: Yeah, with refugees, of course. And you can see it in schools as well. The children who go through this experience suddenly find themselves...they arrive... I mean, in Austria there were quite a lot of refugees from Syria, and I worked closely for almost 20 years in a school that accepted a lot of refugee children because there was a refugee centre close by. And often the children arrived, as we say in German, *quereinsteiger*¹⁸, at the age of eight, nine, ten, without speaking a word of German. But they had a rich repertoire that they brought with them from Syria. They could read and write in Arabic, and often in Kurdish and other languages. Some of them had lived in Turkey for some time. So, there are two, three, four languages they could speak. But just not that German. Once they arrive here, they are usually seen and treated as illiterate, as “voiceless”. And what remains? If you are denied a space or a place from which to speak, what do you do? In contrast, the mentioned school offered an open approach that valorized the children’s resources.

CB: Exactly. It is very important to have a plurilingual approach and not to make people who have four or five languages in their repertoire illiterate just because they don't speak the language of schooling. And moreover, I think that in a traumatic experience, one’s voice may already be broken for other reasons connected to the migratory experience. Perhaps children come to school with a broken voice even in their own languages.

¹⁸ In Austria, *Quereinsteiger* (lit. “sideways entrant”) refers to students who enter the school system not at the beginning of the cycle, but during the year or at a later stage, often coming from another country or education system.

BB: Yes. There's a very good literary text by Marica Bodrožić¹⁹. She's a writer from Bosnia, but she writes in German. She has been living in Germany for many years now. Thinking back to her text, I believe she also lived in Italy for a time; perhaps a translation of her work exists²⁰. When she arrived in Germany, her voice broke – physically, she was no longer able to speak. She couldn't speak in her Dalmatian dialect [born in 1973 in Svib, a small village in Dalmatia, now Croatia, then part of Yugoslavia], nor in German, nor in any other language. When she describes opening her mouth, she says that only a few hoarse sounds came out. And it can become a somatic symptom. She shows how this can become a somatic symptom.

There is another book that describes bodily symptoms caused by a shift in one's repertoire; Aaron Appelfeld also writes about this. He was a writer who passed away, I think, three years ago, and lived in Israel. He was born in what used to be the Austro-Hungarian Empire, but in the eastern part of the country. He was deported with his parents to a concentration camp, but his father allowed him to escape, and as a child he hid in Ukraine, pretending to have no voice, to be mute. And later, he pretended to be Ukrainian. When he finally arrived in Israel, he explained that he could not speak. He could not put words together²¹. These are two writers who describe this somatic-bodily experience of having a repertoire that does not fit, and that suddenly makes you lose the ability to express yourself altogether.

CB: Is this why you talk about using art and drawing to represent one's linguistic repertoire, and why you pay attention to non-linguistic expressive tools? In other words, are you proposing a multimodal approach?

BB: Yes, yes.

CB: It's interesting, if you'd like to go deeper into the multimodal approach to traumatic evidence and plurilingual awareness, in other words, into how word and image can be connected...

¹⁹ Marica Bodrožić (born in 1973 in Svib, Dalmatia, now Croatia) is a German writer and poet of Croatian origin, regarded as one of the most significant voices in German-language migrant literature. Having moved to Germany as a child, she has built her literary identity in the tension between the memory of her Yugoslav childhood, linguistic loss, and the creative appropriation of German as an adopted language.

²⁰ Bodrožić, M. (2010). *È morto Tito* (G. Drago, Trad.). Rovereto: Zandonai. (Original work published in 2002 under the title *Tito ist tot*).

Bodrožić, M. (2012). *Il mio approdo alle parole. Stelle, colori* (B. Ivancic & V. Piazza, Trad.). Roma: Aracne. (Original work published in 2007 under the title *Sterne erben, Sterne färben. Meine Ankunft in Wörtern*).

Bodrožić, M. (2013). *La memoria delle libellule* (I. Amico di Meane, Trad.). Rovereto: Zandonai. (Original work published in 2010 under the title *Das Gedächtnis der Libellen*).

Bodrožić, M. (2017). *Il tavolo di ciliegio* (S. Zangrando, Trad.). Milano–Udine: Mimesis. (Original work published in 2012 under the title *Kirschholz und alte Gefühle*).

²¹ Appelfeld, A. (1994). *Storia di una vita* (trad. A. Shomroni & E. Loewenthal). Milano: Guanda. (*Ed. or. Sipur hayav shel Aharon Appelfeld, 1999; English title: Story of a Life, Schocken Books, 2004*).

Appelfeld, A. (2007). *Il partigiano Edmond e la bambina che amava la neve* (translation A. Shomroni). Milano: Guanda.

BB: I'll first speak about a research project, an interdisciplinary project carried out in a psychiatry ward²². Working with me were an expert in psychosomatic issues and a trauma therapist. We did language portraits because, in medicine or psychiatry in general, multilingualism is often seen as something that makes things more complicated. We wanted to see whether it could instead be transformed into a resource by using language portraits. The setting was like this: there were two professionals and one participant – me as the linguist, and there was either the trauma therapist or the psychotherapist as the psychosomatic expert. And we always made the portrait with one person at a time. We recorded the sessions and found absolutely fascinating results. For instance, there was a woman from Bosnia who drew her portrait by drawing the legs, the arms, and the face, but there was a hole in the middle, a big hole. There was this empty space in the middle. So, we said, “Well, but you left the centre completely empty”, because everything else was filled with very bright colours. And she said, “Yes, I left it empty”. We asked, “Is there a reason?” And she said, “Yeah, it's for Bosnian. I don't like Bosnian. That's why I didn't want to colour it.” So we asked when she spoke Bosnian, etc., and she replied, “With my father”. She didn't want to put Bosnian into the portrait. Then we asked her, “Well, but do you have other resources?” And while we were doing the session, she completed the whole portrait and filled that empty space with a yellow sun for German. We offered the interpretation that she now spoke German so well that it actually replaced Bosnian for her. Then she added some green around it for art therapy, saying that drawing the portrait was art therapy for her. Afterwards, she went back up to the ward and placed the portrait beside her bed, and the therapist on duty said that after drawing the portrait, she participated in a group therapy session for the first time. Before that, she had always refused. From that moment on, she kept the portrait next to her bed. It was very dramatic. I could speak for hours about this experience, because then I asked her whether she knew other languages – like language she used with pets – and she said yes, of course, she had a language for her bird. And she drew a bird in a cage. Both the therapist and I were a bit shocked by the bird in the cage, and she said “Yes, but the cage is important because that way I can protect the bird from my father”. In this way, she expressed herself very clearly.

CB: It's very important to connect the image to the narrative, because in this way she represents things that may be unspeakable, but then she explains them and gives meaning to what she has depicted. The narrative is very important.

EM: Cecilia recounts having had a similar experience with a boy from Côte d'Ivoire who had been asked to draw a tree — a linguistic tree. He put his language, Bambara, at the roots, then French, and then there was a hole, a large hole in the upper part of the trunk, with Italian in the foliage in the colours of the flag. Cecilia, pointing to the hole, asked him, “What is this?” And he replied, “It's my journey, my journey.” As if the migratory journey had *swallowed* his

²² Busch, B. (forthcoming). Linguistic vulnerability: Conceptualizing the language-trauma nexus from an experiential perspective. In J. Purkardhofer, M. Oostendorp, & B. Busch (Eds.), *Routledge Handbook on Language and Trauma*. Milton Park: Routledge.

repertoire. She then commented that, of course, he had spoken many languages during his journey, and initially he had closed himself off. Later, he filled the hole with his languages, although the colour was less solid and the texture was mixed. Most importantly, he drew all the little black dots — representing Bambara — throughout the entire drawing (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: linguistic autobiography represented as a tree

CB: I think it's a therapeutic process. It's a dialogue, isn't it? Because you represent your pain, but it's not just about expressing it — you can make a gesture to transform it into a relationship of listening, with someone. Together, we can think of something different, right?

BB: Yes. Absolutely. This was the portrait I was speaking about. And this is the cage with the bird (shows the portrait). And it was so important for her to be able to put it on paper, even though she did not tell us exactly what had happened to her, but we understood that she had to protect not only the bird, but also herself from her father. And we could feedback that to one of her therapists.

The project was really very interesting and extremely useful. There are several case studies where, in a single portrait session lasting less than an hour, we could learn more about traumatic pasts than in hours and hours of therapy. Because drawing, going beyond the verbal, allows one to express what is difficult to express with words.

Perhaps you know the paper I have on the elephant and the mouse?²³

CB: No, I don't have this one.

BB: But the one of the bird?

²³ Busch, B. (2014). Building on heteroglossia and heterogeneity: The experience of a multilingual classroom. In A. Blackledge & A. Creese (Eds.), *Heteroglossia as Practice and Pedagogy* (pp. 21–40). New York: Springer.

CB: I read the paper in *Applied Linguistics*²⁴.

BB: That's the bird one²⁵. And there is another one about the elephant. I am not sure if I can find it quickly right now. Let's see. Yes, drawings have different affordances from verbal expression. But drawing and verbal together actually create meaning. So, the meaning is distributed across both modalities, if you want. For instance, in one case, a boy drew a story about the elephant and the mouse, but when you analyse the images, you realise he is really talking about his experience as a refugee²⁶. I can send them to you if you want.

EM: Yes, thank you.

BB: It's not so much about the language portrait as it is about the different possibilities of expressing oneself. You've probably heard about the work of Susan Langer, an American philosopher, who worked on the presentational and discursive modes²⁷.

CB: Yes, I found it cited as a reference in your writings.

BB: I think I drew on her work in one of my papers, because she argues that the presentational mode allows contradictions to remain open. You don't have to resolve them. The presentational mode makes it possible not to exclude what cannot be expressed through propositional sequentiality. Often, in the visual, one can access multiple meanings simultaneously, whereas in the discursive mode, one thing comes after another.

But actually, when you wear the clothes, you don't wear them stringed up, but you wear them juxtaposed. And there's relationship between the parts. They form a gestalt, which in itself is a meaning that is more than the sum of its parts. The discursive mode has this linearity, where you have the causal chains, etc. And the presentational mode allows you to express yourself in a more associative way and allows one to express oneself associatively and to leave contradictions unresolved.

So, I think much of the success of the language portrait lies in the fact that it allows one to represent or express things that can simply "be there" and exist in relation to each other. You can say: I put my English in the hand because I use it for social interactions, whereas I put my French in the other hand because I don't like using it in social contexts, or for other reasons.

²⁴ Busch, B., & McNamara, T. (2020) Language and Trauma: An Introduction. *Applied Linguistics*, 41(3), 323–333

²⁵ Busch, B. (2020). Message in a Bottle: Scenic Presentation of the Unsayable. *Applied Linguistics*, 41(3), 408–427

²⁶ Busch, B. (2014). Building on Heteroglossia and Heterogeneity: The Experience of a Multilingual Classroom. In A. Blackledge & A. Creese (Eds.), *Heteroglossia as Practice and Pedagogy* (pp. 21–40). Dordrecht: Springer.

²⁷ The American philosopher Susanne K. Langer (1895–1985), a student of Ernst Cassirer and a central figure in twentieth-century symbolic philosophy, distinguishes in *Feeling and Form* (1953) between discursive forms — characteristic of logical and sequential language — and presentational forms, characteristic of art, which present the structure of feeling rather than describing it. These forms are capable of making visible and shareable what escapes conceptual language. Langer, S. K. (1953). *Feeling and Form: A Theory of Art*. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons.

This allows for comparison, drawing on relationships, and it is also in a way a slower, more reflective mode. On the verbal side, there is pressure – you can't pause too much, even when writing, this pressure is present. Whereas in drawing, there is less pressure from the expectation that there should be no empty space.

CB: Yes, and for the same reason, it's important not to ask too many questions about the drawing. This often happens in schools: children produce images, and the teachers bombard them with questions. But the drawing is not always explainable in words. Of course, it can also be difficult for the teacher when an image expresses something emotionally significant and it's not clear how to "receive" that communication, or how to engage in a meaningful dialogue with the students about that representation.

BB: I mean, when we do language portraits in schools, we usually do it in small groups, only five or six children, not more. And usually while they are drawing, we are already talking with them. So, if you want to record, you need to switch on the recorder almost immediately, and in a group of five or six, discussions can start. Sometimes people say, "Oh, that's not right" and they influence each other, but in reality, it doesn't matter because they are negotiating things among themselves. And that's fine, because in any case, the language portrait develops in interaction. In fact, it never looks the same; in different settings it looks differently, at different moments in time, it looks differently. And it doesn't really matter; one must understand it as a momentarily interactional product.

In schools, we usually do it in small groups, and I usually talk to the children about language philosophical issues. For instance, "Do you know how many languages there are in the world?" I know some will say 2,000, others will say 500, and so on, and then I say, "Okay, yes, so why do you have different estimations and ideas about this?" and their theories come out. Then I ask them, "Okay, UNESCO says this, and the University of Canada-Lavalin says that – why do you think they come up with different numbers?" And then we discuss about languages and dialects, and who decides what counts as a language, and so on. These are children from six to ten years old, and it works well with them. They often say, "Oh, yes, so my language is also a language". There are always children in the group who speak a minority language that isn't officially recognized anywhere. Then we talk about, for example, secret languages and things like that. And we usually discuss language philosophy for five minutes or ten minutes.

CB: It provides a theoretical and reflective legitimation.

BB: Yes, in order to introduce them to the idea of linguistic expression in a broad sense, and so on. They are extremely creative if you start this way. Then we talk about communication. I often ask, for example: "When you wake up in the morning, think through your day. When you wake up, what's the first thing that happens? Do you say good morning to someone, or does someone greet you? Then maybe you turn on the radio, or greet your cat, or something else?" And they start reflecting on their own ways of being and their languages. This really helps them later when they draw their portrait.

CB: Good.

BB: When you stimulate them, you get interesting results.

CB: You have already talked about how your research can be fruitful in a migration context, but maybe we can focus more on this matter.

BB: I mean, many people have used it in a migration context, and we also use it in a migration context in the school I mentioned. I think it can help to value what children bring with them. But I suppose that what is important for me is in the migration context, that is, in schools, is to give children the sense that we respect the resources they bring with them and that we valorise them. Very often, the language portrait represents a way to do this, because they discover that they may not have the language of schooling, but it's not that they don't have a voice—they have many resources available. I think it's a tool that can help raise awareness, if you want, but it very much depends on how it is used, of course. But I know that many people use it in schools. Here, it often happens that teachers assume that when a child comes from a so-called Turkish family or has a Turkish passport, that child necessarily speaks Turkish, which is not necessarily the case, because at home they might very well speak Kurdish, Circassian²⁸ or any other language, and Turkish might actually be their second language. Or for Serbian, very often Serbian is the second language for kids whose first language is Vlach²⁹ or Romani. It can be useful in schools to draw attention to this linguistic repertoire, because we have had quite a lot of problems with teachers who said, "This child does understand neither German nor their own language" We would respond, "Look, but what you call their own language is, of course, their language, but it's a second language, which they learned for very specific purposes".

EM: Of course. You might not remember, but when you arrived in Brno, I mentioned my intention to work by trying to collaborate with the Romani community, the Romani-speaking community, which is very challenging.

BB: Yes, it's hard

EM: So far, I haven't managed to do it. But I think it could be very interesting to work in this direction. Perhaps we could do some work with you as an internal contact in Brno. Maybe we can give it a try. During this summer school, which both of them attended (referring to Cecilia Bartoli and Kristýna Lorenzová), there was a colleague from Prague who works pedagogically with the Romani community. She said that when she tried to conduct research in schools in Prague, she naturally identified several schools with many Romani-speaking

²⁸ The Circassian language belongs to the Northwest Caucasian branch (Abkhaz–Adyghe family) and includes two main varieties, Adyghe and Kabardian–Balcar. It is spoken in the Russian Caucasus and in the Middle Eastern diaspora.

²⁹ Vlach (or Aromanian) is an Eastern Romance language, closely related to Romanian, descended from the Vulgar Latin spoken in the Balkans after Romanization. It is spoken in scattered communities across Greece, Albania, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, and Serbia, with numerous local varieties.

children. But the school principal or director usually claimed that they were not Romani, that they didn't speak Romani at all. I mean, they denied the reality of there being another language, another mother tongue, and considered them only as Czech-speaking children. So, in the Czech Republic, there is a total refusal. I think, therefore, that there is a lot of work to be done.

CB: In this work, in this activity, we run the risk of misinterpretation, don't we? Of reinforcing a stereotypical idea.

BB: I always tell my students that the first interpreter is the author of the portrait. It is actually the author who explains why they chose red or blue or any other colour, and their placement on the body, and so on. It's the metaphorical space that this person has designed for themselves; an interpretation from the outside is not possible. We can only ask questions, but we cannot make assumptions. I believe that generalizing is the great danger. When you start saying, for example, "Yes, the languages charged with emotion are mostly in red" — I mean, there's a bit of truth in that, but it's not always the case. Very often, people choose colours of flags or the arrangement based on ideas about language, emotions, or cultural conventions — but you always have to explore further together with the authors.

CB: Oh, the flag is really recurring.

BB: Yes, but it was really fun. In one of the schools we worked with, they said, "Okay, we draw flags for the different languages," and one girl started drawing a flag with a bone on it and said, "Okay, this is the language of dogs." Then all the other children began drawing every kind of flag. So, in a way, they were pushing nationalism and its emblematic symbols to the extreme, completely subverting them. You can negotiate if you want, and that's what matters. Like in the psychiatric context, we had a participant who was very drawn to the Czech language³⁰. After drawing his entire repertoire, he said, "There's Czech, I know a few words in Czech, and I like going to the Czech Republic," etc. I said, "Well, include it in your portrait," and he replied, "No, I don't want it in my portrait." I thought, "Okay, there's something interesting here." So, we talked about something else, but somehow Czech kept coming up. I thought perhaps his family was a German- or Czech-German-speaking family from the Czech Republic, expelled in 1945. That was my idea. But he categorically refused to include Czech in the portrait. At some point, I began to say my three — really three — words in Czech. He smiled and said, "Yes, yes, exactly. I love pronouncing these words," and so on. Then I asked, "Okay, can these words have a colour?" But he said no. Then he returned to the subject on his own, and suddenly he began telling his story. He said, "Yes, you know, well, in some way, Czech is also my grandfather," and it turned out that his grandfather, whom he loved very much, had a heart attack while he was alone with him as a child and died. It was a total trauma for him, and he had ambivalent feelings toward the Czech language: on one

³⁰ Busch, B. (forthcoming). Linguistic vulnerability: Conceptualizing the language-trauma nexus from an experiential perspective. In J. Purkarthofer, M. Oostendorp, & B. Busch (Eds.), *Routledge Handbook on Language and Trauma*. Milton Park: Routledge.

hand, he was very drawn to it; on the other hand, he couldn't bear to talk about it openly because it meant talking about his grandfather and such. The day after the session, he asked if he could talk with us again, and he spoke a lot about his grandfather and his trips to the Czech Republic, which he now loves visiting, and how good he feels there, and so on. It was really interesting because you could see, on the one hand, these ambivalent feelings, and on the other hand, how the ambivalence was reflected in what he had been unable to express in the portrait. As soon as he realized he could speak and draw, and that we were sharing a few words in Czech, everything, in a sense, unlocked. We really thought this could be useful for therapy, mainly because language has this dual quality. You can talk about a language in a very detached way, saying, "I don't know, my English isn't very good." But in the same sentence, you can also say, "Nevertheless, I like trying to speak when I feel comfortable," or something like that. You can move from talking about your physical sensations, your emotional relationship, to your way of communicating. You can regulate how much you reveal about yourself personally and how much you maintain a sense of distance. You can talk about language as a thing and language as an emotional experience, and this makes it very useful for therapy.

CB: Do you agree that the therapeutic effect is something that happens, but it's not our declared or primary goal?

BB: But you see, what is true for the authors of the portrait can also be true for the other participants and for the teachers. They can also maintain a certain distance, and if the authors talk about their feelings, they don't necessarily have to react accordingly. It depends, in short, on how the interaction is framed. If you want to use it as a therapeutic tool, you can use it as a therapeutic tool. If you want to use it as a tool for linguistic awareness, you can use it as a tool for linguistic awareness.

CB: Yes, yes.

BB: But the truth is that when we do language portraits in schools, sometimes — or more often than one would like — we come across portraits that show a child has problems, that there has been some abuse in the family or elsewhere. I mean, when we conducted large-scale linguistic portrait sessions in schools — almost every school in almost every country where we did them — afterwards we would go to the principal or teacher and say, "Take a look, maybe this child has serious problems." I mean, you may have seen something like this too, when a child makes a very beautiful drawing and then uses black.

CB: Yes, I see that. Often, they erase or draw over it.

BB: And so you know that there might actually be some kind of abuse somewhere, and very often we go to the teacher and say, "Look, there might be something." And very often the teachers respond, "Yes, we already had our doubts about that".

EM: So it stands more for a diagnostic mean than for a therapeutic one.

BB: I couldn't believe how often this happens and everywhere. We had these results in Finland, in Bosnia, in Austria — everywhere. And you can be sure that in a school with, say, 60 or 70 portraits, there will be at least one, if not more, that shows clear traumatic elements.

CB: Yes, it is also necessary for a teacher to first create a language portrait, in order to understand the process that unfolds and to guide their students with awareness.

BB: Yes, I think you're right.

CB: Because it's easier if you know the experience, the feeling, the disappointment, the emotional experience.

BB: Yes, but I think, I mean, still one can regulate very well distance closeness and distance.

CB: In what direction would you like to develop your research in the future?

BB: I don't know. I mean, I'm very curious to know what people want to get out of this work. Currently, our old group, with some members of the previous group and many new members, is working a lot on trauma, on traumatic experiences. Because this has been completely neglected by linguistics. And I think that, in many ways, only through understanding this — through understanding possible traumatic experiences — can various linguistic or sociolinguistic phenomena be understood. That's why we are focusing on this now. But of course, there's much to be done. I mean, one can improve, I don't know, improve the method, document more carefully how the portraits are used and what they mean, what the different inputs signify. Because with the students here, I try to make them understand that what you get depends a lot on the input you provide. It would be nice, for example, to have more detailed documentation of the input phases. But very often, there is a tendency to reproduce the results in an article, and not the interaction and the inputs established by the researchers, so there is no documentation of how the process is handled in the initial phases.

EM: And that is even more general than this specific field, the research in general, we produce, publish outputs and never the process that takes place before.

BB: Yeah, yeah. And I think that's a real problem.

EM: Yeah, definitely. I completely agree with you.

CB: My research focuses on this topic: how a multilingual, multimodal, and narrative approach in a migratory context can serve as a therapeutic space for engaging with the migrant person in an educational setting. School can be a place of "care for the person." It is difficult to find documentation, data, or theoretical research that brings together these three aspects — multilingualism, multimodality, and narration, right? Some focus on multilingualism, others on multimodality, and still others on narration. You are among the

few scholars who have combined these methodological dimensions. I believe this work is very important because migratory experiences often involve traumatic experiences that cannot be ignored in educational contexts.

BB: Yes, migration is a real upheaval in your life. I mean, arriving in an environment where you find yourself thrown into not knowing anything. And yes, for many people it is difficult to understand what that means. Hopefully, this social awareness will grow.

CB: Do you want to say anything more about these narratives represented through images, this research you conducted in the school?

BB: Yes, it's a project we carried out together with the school, and it was called the "Little Books Project"³¹. The children had a corner in the classroom where they could find an envelope with 10 sheets in a small landscape format. Five were for drawing and five for writing, but they could also mix or write or draw more. They could go to this corner at any time during the day, whenever they wanted, and do whatever they wanted. Then they would put their work in an envelope and give it to the teacher. The teacher is the first reader and, together with the child, looks at what they have created and interacts with them. The teacher might say, "Oh, I don't understand this or that. Could you explain it to me?" And then together they can write the book in any language they choose. But together they create a sort of subtitles in German, because German is the lingua franca in the class. This produces an actual little book, and so a library of texts made by the children is created, called "The Little Books Library." By now, they have around a thousand books, or even more. So every child who comes to the school will find in the library box something in their own language, or at least on a topic that interests them. Then the children interact with each other. For example, when one child wrote and drew the story of the mouse and the elephant, someone else took it up and drew another story, or they wrote a book about their birthday, Christmas, or something else. This allows them to express whatever they want. If you look at all the books together, you can see that these are topics that represent the real world of the children at school. You will find computer games, as I said, birthdays, walks in the forest, visits to museums, even hatred of school. There are books about hating school. Basically, there's anything and everything. It was a fantastic project. The teacher is now retired, but he was very good, especially at giving them the possibility to do it at any time of the day, to go there and do it. It's also a way to bring a bit of fresh air into the classroom, because writing about whatever they want is in a way liberating. And there are many books on topics that would normally be taboo, like, for example, video games or things like that.

³¹ Busch, B. (2020). Message in a Bottle: Scenic Presentation of the Unsayable. *Applied Linguistics*, 41(3), 408–427.